

Data management plan (DMP)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

EOSC-SIESTA is developing a platform for the analysis of sensitive data within the European Open Science Cloud, demonstrating the feasibility of adopting FAIR principles throughout the different phases of the data lifecycle. This needs a complete analysis of the data needs and expected results, so that decisions can be made during this initial stage on how to handle the data throughout the project. Our approach aims to ensure the adoption of FAIR principles while facilitating the availability and reusability of the research outputs.

The current document is the initial version of the Data Management Plan (DMP), describing the approach adopted to facilitate data management throughout the entire project lifecycle. The DMP will systematically document and monitor the diverse research artifacts that are needed or will be produced throughout the project, taking into account the particularities of the EOSC-SIESTA project.

We consider data managed or produced by our use cases (UC1: Epidemiology, UC2: Medical Imagine, UC4: Text anonymization and UC5: Demographics) but will also consider other project related assets.

To this aim, this concise document describes the approach that SIESTA consortium is following and relies on the ARGOS service to implement and describe the individual datasets considered.

ARGOS is an open service developed by OpenAIRE to describe and manage the planning of data, supporting different DMP templates (including the Horizon Europe one). ARGOS allows versioning and is a dynamic information service, allowing to seamlessly document and update our initial data management considerations. Thus, the initial DMP and the related ARGOS entries outline the current status and will be regularly updated throughout the project to ensure an up-to-date version and a comprehensive information system encompassing all required research outputs by the project's conclusion.

The different DMP versions will be published in ARGOS and, automatically in Zenodo, which includes a versioning system. The current version of the DMP is already available at Zenodo.

DMP QUESTIONNAIRE

HORIZON EUROPE TEMPLATE

The Horizon Europe Data Management Plan (DMP) Template [1] is an essential tool for researchers and project managers involved in Horizon Europe projects. This template ensures that the management of research data aligns with the principles and requirements of Horizon Europe, promoting transparency, accessibility, and reuse. Although it is not mandatory to follow this template, the list of sections are complete enough to describe all the characteristics of the research outputs from EOSC-SIESTA, so that is why it has been adopted. The following subsections describe the (list of) parts on the DMP template that has been filled by EOSC-SIESTA participants and what approach has been taken to complete the required information.

SECTIONS OF THE HORIZON EUROPE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN TEMPLATE

Due to the diversity of use cases and the research outputs derived from them, rather than following the template to describe each part, it is better to identify those artifacts and detail them separately. In this section, the general approach adopted for creating the SIESTA DMP will be described, and some examples will be added to illustrate it. The template, including some recommendations and tips from the SIESTA point of view, has been sent to the different use cases. They have filled a preliminary version of the different sections, which has been the starting point for completing the information in ARGOS [2].

Data Summary

This section requires a detailed overview of the data that will be generated or reused in the project. Data managers need to specify if they will be reusing any existing data and provide reasons if they decide not to reuse available data. They must describe the types and formats of data to be generated or reused, explaining their purposes and how they relate to the project's objectives. Additionally, researchers should estimate the size of the data and identify its origin or source. The utility of the data outside the project should also be considered, indicating to whom the data might be useful.

For each of the different use cases and the research products identified, this section includes the aforementioned information as well as a brief description of the related use case. There are a diverse number of research inputs or outputs in different formats depending on the use case. In general, the dataset sizes involved are in the order of a few gigabytes and they are in text/tabular format. There are specific use cases like UC2 involving medical images, which involve media formats and bigger size. Regarding the data utility, data and research

products will be useful for the scientific communities as well as policy makers or industry in most of the cases.

FAIR Data

The FAIR data principles [3] —Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability—are crucial for effective data management and to facilitate the understanding of the produced research outputs. Some of the SIESTA objectives are oriented towards demonstrating the feasibility of the FAIR principles over sensitive data in EOSC. Therefore, the proper identification of the characteristics making data and metadata FAIR is important to address the objectives correctly. Also, since SIESTA will adopt FAIR EVA (Evaluator, Validator & Advisor) [4] as a FAIR assessment tool and a plugin will be developed for the project, it is essential to have every component clear. This section is divided into four subsections related to the FAIR principles.

Making Data Findable

Researchers must ensure that data can be easily found by others. This includes using persistent identifiers for the data, providing rich metadata to enable discovery, and using appropriate keywords to optimize searchability. Metadata should be made available in a way that allows it to be harvested and indexed.

Given the initial status of the project, the degree of maturity of the use cases is diverse. In some cases, the data is being reused and already identified, adopting a community-based metadata and data formats or at least essential metadata schemas. To ensure the findability, the use of Persistent Identifiers is critical, so it will be promoted for derived data generated under the EOSC-SIESTA project.

Making Data Accessible

This involves depositing data in trusted repositories and ensuring open access wherever possible. If data cannot be shared openly, researchers need to explain why, distinguishing between legal, contractual, and intentional restrictions. In cases where an embargo period is applied, its duration and justification must be specified. The plan should also describe how access to data will be provided during and after the project, including any necessary authentication procedures and the potential need for a data access committee.

Within the SIESTA project, there are two types of research outputs to be managed. On one hand, data that is already available and generated out of the context of the project is published on both domain-specific repositories (e.g. OpenNeuro) or multidomain ([Zenodo.org](https://zenodo.org)). On the other hand, most of the derived data or research outputs are not yet ready, and decisions need to be made in some of the cases. However, the general approach is to try to publish in domain-

specific FAIR supporting repositories in those cases that are possible, meanwhile generic repositories like Zenodo or DIGITAL.CSIC will be used in the rest of the cases since they are well-known environments supporting FAIR principles. The information regarding accessibility will be updated during the project.

Making Data Interoperable

Researchers should use standard data and metadata formats and vocabularies to ensure that data can be exchanged and reused across different disciplines. They need to follow community-endorsed best practices for interoperability and provide mappings to commonly used ontologies if they use project-specific vocabularies.

Both data and metadata formats selected for inputs or outputs in SIESTA will be standardized or open formats to avoid vendor lock-in. Furthermore, whenever possible, the use of controlled vocabularies will be promoted to increase interoperability. For example, for UC1 oriented to epidemiology, the glossary provided by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has been selected to provide contextual information.

Increasing Data Re-use

Documentation is vital to validate data analysis and facilitate reuse. This includes providing readme files, codebooks, and other relevant information. Data should be made freely available using standard reuse licenses. The provenance of the data must be thoroughly documented, and data quality assurance processes should be described. In few use cases, the input data is already created or available in different sources. In the cases where derived data is generated, proper licenses will be selected, always taking into account the particularities in terms of sensitivity.

Supported by metadata and selecting the proper repository to publish the research outputs, the different use cases will incentivize the reusing. To facilitate data re-use while adhering to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), all data management practices derived from personal or sensitive data will include robust measures for data anonymization and pseudonymization where applicable. Implementing transparent data handling policies and maintaining thorough documentation of consent and data processing activities will not only enhance data re-use but also reinforce trust and legal compliance within the scope of the EOSC-SIESTA project.

Other Research Outputs

In addition to data, researchers should consider other outputs generated or reused during the project, such as software, workflows, protocols, models, new materials, antibodies, reagents, and samples. The same principles applied to

data management should be considered for these outputs to ensure they are managed, shared, and reused effectively.

Due to the initial status of the project, not any research output has been identified yet. ARGOS service will keep the information about data and research output management out to date, as well as the SIESTA GitHub repository² will manage code development for the structural systems as well as the use case functions.

Allocation of Resources

This section requires a detailed plan for the resources needed to make data and other research outputs FAIR. Researchers must outline the costs related to storage, archiving, reuse, and security, and how these costs will be covered. They should identify who will be responsible for data management and how long-term preservation will be ensured, including the necessary resources and decision-making processes. Within EOSC-SIESTA, different institutional or European infrastructures will be used to deposit the outputs, so no extra cost will be incurred. Within the list, we have selected two domain agnostic repositories: Zenodo and DIGITAL.CSIC. Zenodo is a multidisciplinary repository that is widely recognized within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) community. Its robust infrastructure supports a broad range of data types and formats, making it an ideal platform for the diverse datasets generated by the EOSC-SIESTA project. Also, DIGITAL.CSIC is a multidomain repository from the Spanish National Research Council, which is SIESTA coordinator and is involved in different use cases. DIGITAL.CSIC also includes many features to support the publication of FAIR data and allows the inclusion of controlled vocabularies to stimulate the interoperability.

Data Security

Researchers need to detail the provisions in place for data security, including measures for data recovery, secure storage, archiving, and the transfer of sensitive data. The diversity of the use cases implies that this section is detailed separately. In general, the data suitable to be reused has been filtered, or some sensitivity methods have been applied to ensure anonymization.

For those cases where different security procedures need to be performed, they will be detailed after the architecture specification.

Ethics

Any ethical or legal issues that could impact data sharing should be identified and addressed. This includes discussing ethics deliverables and references to the ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA). Researchers must ensure informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation when dealing with personal data. In general, ethics have been considered for the input data and

² <https://github.com/SIESTA-eu>

before the EOSC-SIESTA project, which is reflected in the DMP. For new potential cases, this section will be filled properly.

Due to the sensitive nature of some of the data managed by the project (sensitive personal data, monitoring, further processing of personal data, AI,) an independent Ethics Advisor has been incorporated to report the ethics within the project. The Advisor has expertise on the ethics issues related to vulnerable individuals, special categories of data and AI.

Other Issues

Finally, researchers should mention if they will use other procedures for data management, such as those required by national, funder, sectorial, or departmental guidelines. A brief description of these procedures should be provided to ensure clarity and compliance with additional requirements.

ARGOS

ARGOS, developed through a collaboration between OpenAIRE and EUDAT, provides an open platform for Data Management Planning. It aligns with FAIR and Open best practices, presenting no barriers to use and adoption. ARGOS is available as a standalone service (OpenDMP) and as an OpenAIRE service (ARGOS), simplifying the management, validation, monitoring, and maintenance of Data Management Plans. Researchers, managers, and supervisors can create actionable DMPs that are freely exchangeable among infrastructures, facilitating various aspects of the data management process in accordance with the data owners' intentions and commitments.

ARGOS is integrated within the OpenAIRE platform and is available through the OpenAIRE Service Catalogue as well as the EOSC Catalogue.

ARGOS supports Research Data Management by enabling the creation and publication of Data Management Plans as machine-actionable outputs, which means that the list of identified research output can be linked and dynamic information can be added during the project. These plans are produced as rich text documents following Open and FAIR practices and can be published in open repositories like Zenodo. ARGOS assists in planning data activities at the start of research, documenting processes throughout, and ensuring compliance with institutional or funder requirements. It also includes a catalog of templates that can be selected to complete the DMP.

ARGOS follows a comprehensive DMP publication lifecycle. Users create DMPs, add descriptions for datasets, and share them with colleagues for collaborative writing. Datasets are categorized by type or scientific discipline for better organization.

Given the characteristics of ARGOS and the list of its features, it is the best solution for EOSC-SIESTA. The collaborative functions allow the different use cases responsible access to its research outputs and the information can be

easily updated. Also, we are not completing a static deliverable but providing machine actionable features to a lively service.

One of the most interesting features of ARGOS service is the capacity of exporting the information in different formats, including human-readable ones like PDF or DOCX, but also machine actionable formats like XML or JSON. This is also helpful as a mitigation measure. If ARGOS changes the terms of service, suffers any change or has any legal claim, the information will be easily migrated to any other available system (e.g. DMPonline), tool (e.g. DMP tool) or being up-to-date in any live document or system.

EOSC-SIESTA DMP OVERVIEW

As the project comprises various use cases, the DMP will contain a separate description for each use case. This approach ensures the identification and detailed documentation of the different datasets and research outputs associated with each Use Case. Due to the specific nature of the data involved, rather than creating a single overarching DMP, the Horizon Europe DMP template will be individually completed for each Use Case. The following figure illustrates an overview of the primary information pertaining to the project.

The link to the updated DMP is: <https://zenodo.org/records/12546352>

As the project is still in its early stages, the research outputs may change as EOSC-SIESTA progresses. The current use cases are briefly described below:

UC1: Epidemiology [Synthetic Populations and Building Information]

The objective of the Use Case 1 (WP14) is to develop an ecosystem in the SIESTA platform, and by extension in EOSC, able to use data to perform computational epidemic predictions. For this, synthetic populations for France, Italy and Spain need to be built to feed models versatile enough for external users to define the particular epidemic process to be analyzed. The input data comes from different sources that are described in the DMP in some cases including sensitive data that is anonymized. In this case, the potential research output is the synthetic populations.

UC2: Medical Imaging

This Use Case 2 (WP15) aims at deploying different data processing pipelines on sensitive medical (neuro)imaging data in a safe environment. It is divided into separate example sub-cases to ensure a sufficiently wide identification of data

characteristics (from small to large, from simple to complex), analysis characteristics (short and long computations, different computational tools), user interactions, and eventual SIESTA platform requirements. The example pipelines are developed and documented using existing representative input data that is available in public repositories. It includes information about the formats and metadata schemas from the input data, details about the pipelines and the potential output data to be produced.

UC4: Text anonymization on sensitive data [Output Data]

In some domains, such as cybersecurity, crime or cybercrime prevention, there is a need to classify unstructured text (e.g., Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT) or crime reports) into categories. This classification is prone to be automatized, but the data needed to train the classification models often contain sensitive or private data (e.g. names, locations, IPs, etc.), so such data cannot be disclosed by the interested authorities. Therefore, the models cannot be trained and, consequently, the automatic classification of such reports is not possible. This use case will focus on the anonymization of non-structured text containing sensitive data, with a focus on the subsequent text classification: the anonymized text should be useful to train models that can classify the original (i.e. non-anonymized texts) with an analogous performance as if the model was trained with the original texts. The description of this Use Case in the DMP includes details about the potential output data to be produced.

UC5: Demographics

Socio-demographic and health microdata, which are frequently produced by public administrations, have an important value to researchers from a wide spectrum of scientific disciplines. The access to this information requires the “signature of agreements”, clearance of users and the use of physical secured rooms. SIESTA will provide a set of tools to improve the anonymization of the data to be shared, the creation of designed populations whose data can be shared without privacy concerns and systems to analyze in a reproducible FAIR way the data without the need of a direct access and the implementation of a pilot Intermediate Data Center. This will reduce the burden that statistical offices have on preparing tailored data for individual requests which takes their time from other statistical production, and will allow a wider re-use of statistical and administrative data. The DMP will update with the details about which data will be incorporated into the platform for testing proposes as well as the potential output to be produced for reusing, taking into account that, at least at the beginning, it will be treated as a proof of concept.

CONCLUSIONS

The content of this deliverable “D1.2 - Initial Data Management Plan” is an overview of the approach adopted to take decisions regarding the data management in EOSC-SIESTA project. Rather than being the DMP itself, it presents the structure to be found in the ARGOS system, where all the different data components and research outputs are described, and where the information will be regularly updated during the project. It also describes some examples of the information that can be found in ARGOS, including the different Use Cases participating in the project.

Although ARGOS will be the place to find up-to-date information about the data management in SIESTA, Deliverable 2.2 “Updated DMP” will complete the current deliverable with any new identified data or research output, as well as any new approach adopted within the project.

REFERENCES

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